

Do general dental practitioners use sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine as an irrigation material during pulpectomy treatment? A cross-sectional study

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Abstract— Background: The aim of the study was to evaluate knowledge and attitude of general dental practitioners regarding use of sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine during pulpectomy treatment in children.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted with 201 general dental practitioners with qualification of BDS, MDS-Pedodontics, MDS-Other than Pedodontics to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding use of sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine as an irrigation material during pulpectomy. Statistical analysis was done by using descriptive and inferential statistics using chi square test and software used in the analysis was SPSS 27.0 version and $p < 0.05$ is considered as level of significance.

Results: A significantly low percentage of general dental practitioners possessing MDS in Pedodontics, compared to those with BDS or MDS Other than Pedodontics, demonstrated uncertainty regarding the essentiality, concentration, and potential complications of sodium hypochlorite, and the essentiality and concentration of chlorhexidine, as irrigation materials for pulpectomy or re-pulpectomy procedures in necrotic teeth.

Conclusion: Among general dental practitioners, BDS and MDS-Other than Pedodontics have moderate knowledge and MDS-Pedodontics were up to date regarding the knowledge about the irrigation materials used during pulpectomy treatment.

Keywords— children, chlorhexidine (CHX), dental treatment, general dental practitioners (GDPs), pulpectomy, sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl).

I. INTRODUCTION

The major reason for pulp treatment in deciduous teeth is to keep teeth in place in the dental arch. Among all vital and nonvital pulp treatments, pulpectomy is commonly used treatment option in paediatric patients whose primary teeth are diagnosed with irreversible pulpitis to prevent early primary teeth exfoliation or need for extraction later.[1] The primary goal of any endodontic procedure is the complete removal of bacteria from the root canal system and the avoidance of subsequent re-infection. The clinician's key to endodontic treatment success is a clean and sterile root canal system.[2]

Endodontic treatment of primary teeth is thought to be quite challenging due to their peculiar internal geometry and other characteristics that are not prevalent in permanent teeth, such as furcational connections and horizontal anastomoses.[3] For this very obvious reason, in order to completely debride and disinfect the root canal, irrigation and instrumentation best works in tandem.[4]

Presently irrigation materials can be divided into antibacterial, decalcifying, or a mix of these agents. Since, no single irrigating solution is thought to be ideal till date, using two or more in a precise

order increases the likelihood that a treatment will be successful.[3] Among all the material used for irrigation in primary teeth, most commonly used clinically are sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and chlorhexidine (CHX). When used in concentrations of 0.5 % which is the most commonly used concentration, NaOCl functions as an effective antibacterial agent that instantly eliminates bacteria from the root canals.[3] On the other side, actinomyces israelii and enterococcus faecalis are two root canal pathogens that are significantly inhibited by 2% CHX.[5]

Literature search shows scarcity of information regarding the knowledge and attitude of general dental practitioners (GDPs) towards the use of irrigation materials such as NaOCl and CHX.[6] Therefore, the study was conducted with the aim, to evaluate knowledge and attitude regarding use NaOCl and CHX as an irrigation material during pulpectomy treatment in children amongst GDPs in Maharashtra, India.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

After taking the consent from Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC), a cross-sectional study regarding the use of irrigation materials during pulpectomy, was conducted among GDPs in Maharashtra, India. Convenience sampling technique was used in the study. Sample size is calculated using below mentioned formula

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

According to study done by Patil P. et al [7] and reference for formula by Cochran W.G. [8], If population is more than 10,000 with,

Z: statistic for a level of confidence. (For the level of confidence of 95%, which is conventional, Z value is 1.96)

P: expected prevalence or proportion. (P is considered 0.5)

d: precision. (d is considered 0.05 to produce good precision and smaller error of estimate)

After calculations, sample size (n) = 190.46

So, the sample size of the study calculated is set at 200 participants.

The GDPs who were qualified as Bachelor of Dental Surgery (BDS) and Masters of Dental Surgery (MDS) and practicing in Maharashtra, India were included and classified into three groups viz. BDS, MDS – Pedodontist (MDS-P), MDS - Other Than Pedodontist (MDS-OTP). Individuals who were not willing to share all the information for this study, dental graduates not practicing dentistry, post graduate students, under graduate students were excluded from the study.

A closed-ended questionnaire comprised of 17 questions was prepared to assess the knowledge and attitude of GDPs regarding use of NaOCl and CHX as an irrigation material during pulpectomy treatment in children in Maharashtra. The questionnaire was sent either through email or mobile-based applications like Facebook or WhatsApp and data collection was done. The collected data entered in an excel spreadsheet, statistically analysed and inferences were drawn accordingly. Statistical analysis was done by using descriptive and inferential statistics using chi square test and software used in the analysis was SPSS 27.0 version and p<0.05 is considered as level of significance.

III.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In present study, GDPs participated in very wide age range from 24 years to 58 years. Total 201 GDPs responded to the questionnaire out of 700 whom it was sent. Majority of which were females with around 54.20%. Number of practitioners who were BDS were 65 (30.92%), MDS practitioner who were pedodontist (MDS-P) were 60 (29.85%) and MDS practitioner who were not pedodontist (MDS-OTP) were 76 (37.81%). Most of GDPs clinical experience was between 1 to 5 years without any statistically significant difference (p=0.16).

When participants were asked regarding the frequency of pulpectomy treatment 42.30% answered most often, 26.90% answered often and 30.80% answered least often. When asked about irrigating solution they use during pulpectomy, 79.60% participants answered normal saline, 68.20% answered sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and 23.40% answered chlorhexidine (CHX). When asked about the irrigation protocol for primary and permanent teeth then 68.70% opted that there is difference, 12.90% opted no difference and 18.4% were not sure regarding the protocol. The possible reason for the difference in the protocol is because of the anatomical variations in primary teeth root canals when compared to permanent teeth.[9]

When questioned about essentiality of irrigation with NaOCl during pulpectomy 67.66% opted yes, 16.42% opted no and 15.92% were not sure. Among all the participants who were not sure 21.54% were BDS and 19.74% were MDS-OTP while only 5% were MDS-P so this result was statistically significant with p=0.042. 91% participants were aware of toxicity of NaOCl to vital oral tissue while 3% were not aware and 6% were not sure. These results were in contrast to the study done by Sadeep et.al., in which 71.8% participants were aware with the fact.[10] When asked about the concentration of NaOCl which can be effectively used in children the results were statistically significant as shown in Table I. Many researchers suggested the use of NaOCl in concentration with 0.5% to 5.25% but most common being 0.5% considering the risk of its accident.[3]

TABLE I
CONCENTRATION OF SODIUM HYPOCHLORITE CAN BE EFFECTIVELY USED IN CHILDREN

Question	Option	BDS	MDS-P	MDS - OTP	Total	p-value
How much concentration of sodium hypochlorite can be effectively used in children?	0.5%	44.62%	28.33%	38.16%	75 (37.31%)	p=0.0001
	1%	9.23%	55%	14.47%	50 (24.88%)	
	3%	6.15%	10%	9.21%	17 (8.46%)	
	5.25%	15.38%	1.67%	11.84%	20 (9.95%)	
	Not Sure	24.62%	5%	26.32%	39 (19.40%)	

When asked regarding the use and reason for usage of NaOCl, the results were statistically significant with p=0.002 which is shown in Table II. When asked regarding prevention of NaOCl accident the 86.10 % participants opted all the options such as use of side-vented needle, concentration of NaOCl solution used, rubber dam isolation and by avoiding binding of syringe inside the canal. These results were

in contrast to the results in study done by Sadeep et.al, in which 50.5% of participants answered all of the above-mentioned options.[10]

TABLE II
USE AND REASON FOR USING AND NOT USING OF NAOCL

Question	Option	BDS	MDS-P	MDS - OTP	Total	p-value
Do you use sodium hypochlorite solution as an irrigating solution? If not is there any fear of sodium hypochlorite accident in children?	Yes, I use sodium hypochlorite solution	40%	76.67%	48.68%	109 (54.23%)	p=0.002
	No, I have fear of sodium hypochlorite accident	27.69%	16.67%	18.42%	39 (19.40%)	
	No, I don't think sodium hypochlorite is necessary	16.92%	10%	18.42%	31 (15.42%)	
	Not Sure	15.38%	1.67%	14.47%	22 (10.95%)	

When questioned about essentiality of irrigation with CHX during pulpectomy 68.33% MDS-P opted yes and only 10% were not sure about its use while 38.46% BDS and 38.16% of MDS-OTP were not sure about its use. So, the results were statistically significant with p=0.002 as shown in Table III. When asked about concentration of CHX used for irrigation during pulpectomy 43.33% MDS-P correctly answered it as 2% while only 26.15% of BDS and 27.63% MDS-OTP were opted for the same. Again, the results were statistically significant with p=0.002 as shown in Table III. The knowledge of the MDS-P participants was quite up to date for concentration and use of chlorhexidine.[3]

TABLE III
ESSENTIALITY AND CONCENTRATION OF CHX

Question	Option	BDS	MDS-P	MDS - OTP	Total	p-value
Do you think, irrigation with chlorhexidine is essential during pulpectomy?	Yes	43.08%	68.33%	40.79%	100 (49.75%)	p=0.002
	No	18.46%	21.67%	21.05%	41 (20.40%)	
	Not Sure	38.46%	10%	38.16%	60 (29.85%)	
How much concentration of chlorhexidine can be effectively used in children?	0.2%	20%	31.67%	43.42%	65 (32.34%)	p=0.002
	1%	9.23%	3.33%	9.21%	15 (7.46%)	
	2%	26.15%	43.33%	27.63%	64 (31.84%)	
	Not Sure	44.62%	21.67%	19.74%	57 (28.36%)	

When questioned about the irrigation solution used in a necrotic tooth during pulpectomy with options provided were normal saline, NaOCl, CHX, all of the above and not sure, then 66.67% MDS-P opted for all that is normal saline, NaOCl and CHX. 20% of BDS, 10.53% of MDS-OTP and only 5% were not sure about use of irrigation material asked regarding same question and the results were statistically significant with $p=0.029$ as shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
IRRIGATING MATERIAL USED IN NECROTIC AND RE-PULPECTOMY CASES

Question	Option	BDS	MDS-P	MDS - OTP	Total (n=201)	p-value
Which of the following Irrigation solution must be used in a necrotic tooth during pulpectomy procedure?	Normal Saline	10.77%	10%	10.53%	21 (10.45%)	$p=0.029$
	Sodium Hypochlorite	9.23%	8.33%	21.05%	27 (13.43%)	
	Chlorhexidine	4.62%	10%	13.16%	19 (9.45%)	
	All of the above	55.38%	66.67%	44.74%	110 (54.73%)	
	Not Sure	20%	5%	10.53%	24 (11.94%)	
In failed pulpectomy cases; which of the following irrigating material must be use in such re-pulpectomy cases?	Normal Saline	1.54%	3.33%	1.32%	4 (1.99%)	$p=0.014$
	Sodium Hypochlorite	38.46%	30%	44.74%	77 (38.31%)	
	Chlorhexidine	30.77%	56.67%	30.26%	77 (38.31%)	
	Not Sure	29.23%	10%	23.68%	43 (21.39%)	

The possible factor for less usage of CHX is the inadequate knowledge about use of newer irrigating materials; as the participants in BDS group were mostly senior practitioners. In current study, when asked about the use of irrigation material that is must be used during re-pulpectomy cases where *E. faecalis* and *A. israelii* is the most commonly found micro-organism then around 56.67% MDS-P opted the correct option that is CHX while 30.77% of BDS and 30.26% MDS-OTP opted the same and only 10% MDS-P were not sure about the irrigation material used. These results were statistically significant with $p=0.014$ as shown in Table IV. The difference in the groups may be because of lack of knowledge in GDPs that 2% CHX is significantly effective against root canal pathogens like *A. israelii* and *E. faecalis*. [5]

The possible limitations for the current study are

- A. Only two irrigation materials which are commonly used were asked regarding its use. We could have observed some change in results if there is addition of other irrigation materials.

- B. The results were not drawn considering the participants of MDS-OTP are inclusive of MDS endodontics among them. MDS endodontics may have better knowledge regarding irrigation materials when compared with other dental practitioners.

IV. CONCLUSION

The General dental practitioners often perform pulpectomy procedures. This study emphasizes that among GDPs; BDS and MDS-OTP have moderate knowledge and MDS-P were up to date to the knowledge about the irrigation materials used during pulpectomy procedures. These types of studies are useful for determining whether our opinions or methods are consistent with current trends. It seems essential that higher education bodies should incorporate a protocol for use of irrigation materials during pulpectomy in children to enhance the knowledge of GDPs regarding the treatment.

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